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THE FACTORS AND CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING THE STATE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF WORKING CAPITAL UTILIZATION IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstracts. *The article is devoted to the analysis of key factors affecting the efficiency of the use of working capital in agriculture. The article discusses: problems and features of working capital management in agricultural organizations, due to the seasonality of production, the cyclical turnover; the specifics of agribusiness. The key factors affecting the efficiency of working capital use are inventory optimization, accounts receivable management, and shortening the turnover period of working capital.*

Key words: *efficiency, working capital, turnover, turnover duration, acceleration of turnover, release of resources.*

ФАКТОРЫ И КРИТЕРИИ ОЦЕНКИ СОСТОЯНИЯ И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ОБОРОТНЫХ СРЕДСТВ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена анализу ключевых факторов, влияющих на эффективность использования оборотного капитала в сельском хозяйстве. В статье рассматриваются: проблемы и особенности управления оборотным капиталом в сельскохозяйственных организациях, обусловленные сезонностью производства, цикличностью оборота, спецификой агробизнеса. Ключевыми факторами, влияющими на эффективность использования оборотного капитала, являются оптимизация запасов, управление дебиторской задолженностью, сокращение периода оборачиваемости оборотного капитала.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективность, оборотный капитал, оборачиваемость, продолжительность оборота, ускорение оборачиваемости, высвобождение ресурсов.*

A significant part of agricultural organizations has lost their own working capital; reserves of self-sufficiency in production stocks are sharply narrowed; opportunities for purchasing material resources of industrial production are limited, the lack of which was one of the main reasons for the decline in the level of intensification in agriculture. Significant reserves of sustainable development and profitability of agricultural production are laid in the effective use of current assets [1].

In the system of measures aimed at improving the efficiency of agricultural organizations and strengthening their financial condition, an important place is occupied by the rational use of working capital. This problem has become even more urgent in the conditions of market relations formation. The interests of agricultural producers require from them full responsibility for the results of their financial and economic activities. Due to the fact that the financial position of organizations is in direct dependence on the state of current assets and implies the commensurability of costs with the results of economic activity, reimbursement of costs by own funds, the interests of effective use of current assets require the organization of their movement in the minimum possible volume to obtain the greatest economic effect [2].

In turn, the efficiency of working capital utilization depends on various factors. Among them we can distinguish external factors that influence independently of the interests and sphere of activity of an agricultural enterprise, and internal factors that the enterprise can and, moreover, should actively influence. The external factors include: general economic situation, peculiarities of tax legislation, conditions for obtaining loans and interest rates on them, possibility of target financing, participation in programs financed from the budget. Taking into account these and other external factors, the enterprise can use internal reserves by increasing the economic efficiency of the use of working capital [8]. Factors affecting the efficiency of working capital utilization are presented in the figure below.

System of factors of efficiency of working capital utilization

At the current stage of economic development, the most important external factors affecting the state and use of working capital include: price disparity for agricultural products and material and technical resources, high level of taxes, non-payment crisis and high rates of bank credit, as a result of which credit resources become simply unaffordable for the majority of agricultural producers [4, 6].

Still insufficient is the amount of subsidies to compensate part of the costs of purchasing various material resources (spare parts, mineral fertilizers, chemical plant protection products, etc.), the share of which in production costs is 68%, and in recent years their share tends to increase due to the increase in purchase prices. This factor mainly determines the dynamic increase in the cost of production and, accordingly, negatively affects both the efficiency of agricultural production in general and the efficiency of working capital utilization in particular. That is, we can say that, for the most part, external factors have a negative impact on the activities of agricultural producers, causing a decrease in the efficiency of their working capital utilization [3].

Thus, it is obvious that the main reserves for improving the efficiency of working capital use should be identified and implemented directly in the agricultural organization itself.

The financial position of the enterprise, its solvency and liquidity are in direct dependence on how quickly the funds invested in assets turn into real money. The growth of non-payments complicates the rhythmic activity of the enterprise and leads to an increase in accounts receivable.

At the same time, excessive diversion of funds into production inventories, work in progress, finished goods leads to dead resources and inefficient use of working capital [5].

The rate of turnover of funds depends on the size of the annual turnover, the need for additional sources of financing and payment for them, the amount of costs associated with the possession of inventory and their storage, etc.

The duration of the circulation of the funds is determined by the combined influence of external and internal factors. External factors include the scope and scale of the enterprise's activities, industry affiliation, the nature of economic ties with partners, influence of inflation processes etc. n. Internal factors should include the price policy of the enterprise, asset structure and strategy for their management, methods of valuation of goods inventory etc. [9].

Since the criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of working capital management is time, their turnover is characterized by a number of interrelated indicators reflecting, first, total turn time, or the duration of one turn in days; second, the speed of turn is the number of turns over a given period (turnover ratio) [6].

In addition to the above factors and criteria for evaluating the state and effectiveness of working capital utilization in agriculture may include:

1. Current Ratio: This ratio measures the ability of a farm to meet its short-term obligations with its current assets. A higher current ratio indicates a healthier financial position.

2. Inventory Turnover Ratio: This ratio shows how efficiently a farm is managing its inventory. A higher turnover ratio indicates that inventory is being sold quickly, which can improve cash flow.

3. Accounts Receivable Turnover: This ratio measures how quickly a farm collects payments from its customers. A higher turnover ratio indicates effective credit management.

4. Accounts Payable Turnover: This ratio measures how quickly a farm pays its suppliers. A lower turnover ratio may indicate that the farm is taking longer to pay its bills, which can impact relationships with suppliers.

5. Cash Conversion Cycle: This metric measures the time it takes for a farm to convert its investments in inventory and other resources into cash flow from sales. A shorter cash conversion cycle is generally more favorable.

By analyzing these factors and criteria, farmers can assess the efficiency of their working capital management and make informed decisions to improve their financial performance in agriculture.

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